

ISic3445

I.Sicily inscription 3445

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

necropolis of S. Ippolito

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 8563

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644923

EDCS 70900749

Bibliography

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 107 no.5

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